

A STUDY ON WORKPLACE STRESS AMONG INSURANCE SECTOR EMPLOYEES (A COMPARITIVE ANALYSIS BETWEEN LIC AND EXIDE LIFE INSURANCE)

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Abstract— Insurance sector is one of the crucial sectors in the infrastructural sectors that is providing economic security to millions of individuals across the nation. But it is no exaggeration to say that employees of almost all insurance companies are going through acute workplace stress. This is because of ever-increasing pressure to beat out competitors. Moreover, insurance products are such that due to the low awareness among public about their utility, it is very challenging for the agents to publicize insurance products and market them. The result is acute levels of stress among employees working in insurance sector. With the growing number of players in private insurance sector, even public sector insurance companies like LIC has to struggle a lot to attract the public. Hence, the present study aims at studying and analyzing the causes of stress among employees of public as well as private sector insurance companies..

Keywords—Life Insurance, Stress, High targets, strategies, stress management

I. INTRODUCTION

“Unless one is immortal, one needs life insurance” goes the saying. Insurance, especially life insurance has become an obvious choice for almost everyone.

Insurance sector has shown incredible growth in the recent years. Earlier, only two Insurance companies were there in India – Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC) and General Insurance Corporation of India (GIC). Indian Insurance sector comprise of 24 Life Insurance and 24 General Insurance companies which offer various innovative products keeping in mind the different needs of people. Most of these companies have entered the market in collaboration with International firms¹. The increase in number of players in Private sector insurance sector, even Public sector insurance companies like LIC has to struggle not only to attract clients but even to delight them and achieve sustained business development. This phenomenon has brought many changes in the working styles of insurance companies. More than 5,00,000 employees are working in various insurance companies, both in public and private sector. As the competition is going to its peaks, targets for insurance agents have also grown tremendously. The obvious result is stress among employees working in insurance sector. It is not exaggerating to say that the heartbeat of agents go up when it is the time of end of a performance appraisal period. Working in Insurance sector poses lot of challenges because right from attracting clientele

to satisfying all the claims of clients, insurance sector employees have to undergo lot of activities. The obvious result of these is stress. High levels of stress lead to mental as well physical health issues among employees working in insurance sector.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

W.J. Coetzer and S. Rothmann, in their article entitled, “Occupational stress of employees in an insurance company”, made an attempt to study and analyze the relationship between occupational stress and commitment towards the organizations. The researchers in their research found out that job insecurity and work related stress are the two main causes of poor organizational commitment among employees working in insurance sector^[1].

Arul Edison Anthony Raj, Dr. Sheeba Julius²(2018), in their article entitled, “Occupational Stress among employees working in an Insurance Company: An empirical Study”, studied the occupational factors responsible for stress among insurance sector employees and analyzed the relationship between occupational Stress and organizational commitment. They concluded that occupational stress has an important bearing on Organizational Commitment and role ambiguity, job insecurity are the major causes of employee stress.

Bhanwar Singh³(2017), in his article entitled, “Job Stress among employees in Insurance Sector” and studied the gender specificity or neutrality of various factors responsible for job stress. His study concluded that job stress is gender neutral in most of the cases.

R. Mohanaselvi and S. Manimaran⁴(2016), in their article entitled, “A study on stress among consultants in Insurance sector in Dindugal”, studied and analyzed stress among insurance consultants in public and private sectors. They observed that role ambiguity, over workload etc are the main causes of stress and stress has its impact on both personal and Professional life

Prakash b. Kudaragi and A M Kadakol⁵(2017), in their article “A study on stress management of LILC employees in Belgavi District” studied the techniques followed by employees of LIC to overcome stress. They found that proper planning of work commitments and maintaining work life balance are the most effective strategies for managing stress.

Sneha Mankikar⁶(2014), in her article entitled, “Stress Management in insurance sector, A veracity check”, studied the cause and effect of stress among employees working in insurance sector. Her study observed that there is a greater relationship

between employee remuneration and occupational stress. She even observed that women employees are more stressed out than their male counterparts.

Vinay Kumar⁷(2016), in his article entitled, "Workplace stress among employees in Insurance sector, A study", studied the main causes and effects of workplace stress. He found that both male and female employees are facing workplace stress and they are somewhat happy with their management with respect to the strategies they adopt to remove stress among employees.

Research Gap: Though many previous researchers attempted to study the stress among employees working in Insurance sector, not much of them concentrated on whether stress is significantly different among employees working in Public Sector and LIC. Hence the researcher made an attempt to find out the stress among employees of both public sector and private sector insurance companies.

III OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study is carried out with the following objectives.

1. To identify factors causing stress among employees in public and private sector insurance companies.
2. To assess whether the stress levels among employees in public and private sector insurance companies significantly differ or not.
3. To study and analyze the stress management techniques adopted by employees.

IV -RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study is mainly based on Primary data collected from two main Insurance companies, Life Insurance corporation of India (Public Sector) and Exide Life Insurance Corporation (Private Sector). Samples of 644 respondents were consulted on a convenient basis to gather opinions on what made them stressful at work.

V.HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY:

H0: There is no significant difference between stress among employees in public sector insurance companies and private sector insurance companies.

H1: There is significant difference between stress among employees in public sector insurance companies and private sector insurance companies.

VI - RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table: 1

Components	Exide Life Insurance		LIC	
	Number	%	Number	%
AGE				
20-28	20	32.0	25	4.30
29-38	10	16.0	75	12.89
39-48	20	32.0	200	34.36
49 & Above	12	19.0	282	48.45
GENDER				
Male	50	80.6	450	77.32%
Female	12	19.4	132	22.68%
MARITAL STATUS				
Married	45	72.58	460	79.04%
Unmarried	17	27.42	122	20.96%
MONTHLY INCOME				
Below 20,000	5	0.081	75	12.887
20,000-40,000	20	32.258	80	13.746

40,000-60,000	20	32.258	250	42.955
Above 60,000	17	27.419	177	30.412

Table 2:

Sl. No.	Choice of response	Public Sector insurance employees	Private sector employees	Total
1	Strongly agree	53.22%	43.13%	44.10%
		33	251	284
2	Agree	30.64%	38.49%	37.73%
		19	224	243
3	Undecided	9.67%	8.25%	8.38%
		6	48	54
4	Disagree	6.45%	10.14%	9.78%
		4	59	63
5	Strongly disagree	-	-	-
Total		100%	100%	100%
		62	582	644
Weighted average mean score		4.31	4.15	4.16
Chi square test values		Calculated value-3.124	Table value-7.815	
Anova test values.		C value: 5.8239	T value: 5.987	
T test values		C value: - 2.4132	T value: 2.446	

CHI SQUARE TEST, ANOVA TEST and T-TEST

The data are also tested with the help of statistical values. In this regard, Chi square test, ANOVA Test and T test have been conducted, The results of the Chi Square test show that the calculated value is at 3.124 while the table value at 5% level of significance stands at 7.815. Since the calculated value is less than that of the table value, the null hypothesis is accepted. Even the ANOVA Test and T test results substantiate the above observation. It shows that most of the employees working in Insurance sector feel frustrated to work. The following diagram depicts the opinion of respondents on whether they feel frustrated in their work.

Figure.1

Table: 3

Sl. No.	Choice of response	Exide Life Insurance	LIC	Total
1	High and unachievable targets	56.45%	43.13%	44.41%
		35	251	286
2	Lack of superior support	32.26%	39.86%	39.13%
		20	232	252
3	Lack of Customer Network	8.06%	9.62%	9.47%
		5	56	61
4	Lack of marketing skills	3.22%	7.39%	6.98%
		2	43	45
5	Extended hours of work	-	-	-
Total		100%	100%	100%
		62	582	644
Weighted average mean score		4.42	4.19	4.21
Chi square values		Calculated value: 4.601	Table value: 7.815	
Anova test values		C value: 5.3619	T value: 5.987	
T test values		C value: - 2.3155	T value: 2.446	

An analysis of the opinions of Exide Life Insurance and LIC employees reveals the following. Among the Exide Life Insurance, majority of them who accounts for 56.45 percent stated that high and unachievable targets are the main cause of stress. Those who follow it and who account for 32.26percent

said that lack of superiors' support is the cause of their stress. In the remaining sample, people who said lack marketing skills is the cause of their stress are relatively more than those who said extended hours of work is the cause of their stress. In this regard, Chi square test, ANOVA Test and T test have been conducted, The results of the Chi Square test show that the calculated value is at 4.601 while the table value at 5% level of significance stands at 7.815. Since the calculated value is less than that of the table value, the null hypothesis is accepted. Even the ANOVA Test and T test results substantiate the above observation. It reveals that most of the employees working in both public sector insurance sector and private sector insurance sector employees are stressed out for one reason or the other. When asked whether they agree that spending time with family reduces work-related stress or not, the respondents' responses were as below.

Table: 4

S. No	Choice of response	Exide Life Insurance	Private sector insurance employees	Total
1	Strongly agree	43.55%	45.02%	44.88%
		27	262	289
2	Agree	56.45%	47.25%	48.14%
		35	275	310
3	Undecided	-	7.73%	6.98%
			45	45
4	Disagree	-	-	-
5	Strongly disagree	-	-	-
Total		100%	100%	100%
		62	582	644
Weighted average mean score		4.44	4.37	4.38
Chi square test values		Calculated value: 5.806	Table value: 5.991	
Anova test values		C value: 5.2928	T value: 7.7086	
T test values		C value: - 2.3	T value: 2.776	

The results of the Chi Square test show that the calculated value is at 5.806 while the table value at 5% level of significance stands at 5.991. Since the calculated value is less than that of the table value, the null hypothesis is accepted. Even the ANOVA Test and T test results substantiate the above observation. It indicates that the most of the respondents agreed that spending time with family reduces stress.

When asked if involving in meditation and Yoga reduces work-related stress, the respondent's reactions were as below.

Table:5

Sl. No.	Choice of response	Exide Life Insurance	LIC employees	Total
1	Strongly	54.84%	41.92%	43.17%

	agree	34	244	278
2	Agree	45.16%	50.86%	50.31%
		28	296	324
3	Undecided	-	5.67%	5.12%
			33	33
4	Disagree	-	1.55%	1.40%
			9	9
5	Strongly disagree	-	-	-
Total		100%	100%	100%
		62	582	644
Weighted average mean score		4.55	4.33	4.35
Chi square test values		Calculated value: 7.001	Table value: 7.815	
Anova test values		C value: 3.1383	T value: 5.987	
T test values		C value: - 1.7715	T value: 2.446	

When asked about the strategies adopted by their management to reduce stress levels among their employees, the respondents' responses were as below

Table: 6

Sl. No.	Choice of response	Exide Life Insurance	LIC employees	Total
1	Conduct employee counseling	53.23%	41.58%	42.70%
2	Provide recreational facilities	38.71%	47.77%	46.89%
3	Improve working conditions	4.84%	7.04%	6.83%
4	Provide training to cope up with stress	3.22%	3.65%	3.57%
5	Ignores the employee stress	-	-	-
Total		100%	100%	100%
		62	582	644

Weighted average mean score	4.42	4.27	4.29
Chi square test values	Calculated value: 3.181	Table value: 7.815	
Anova test values	C value: 3.7551	T value: 5.987	
T test values	C value: -) 1.9378	T value: 2.446	

Table-6 presents the opinions of sample respondents about the strategies adopted by the management to reduce the stress levels among employees. Among the total sample respondents, majority of them who accounts for 46.89 percent said that their managements provide recreational facilities to their employees to deal with their stress. Those who follow it and who account for 42.70 percent said that their managements counsel the employees to cope up with stress. Chi square test, ANOVA Test and T test have been conducted, The results of the Chi Square test show that the calculated value is at 3.181 while the table value at 5% level of significance stands at 7.815. Since the calculated value is less than that of the table value, the null hypothesis is accepted. Even the ANOVA Test and T test results substantiate the above observation. It shows that both in Public sector Insurance sectors and in Private sector insurance sectors, managements take certain steps to reduce the stress levels among their employees.

CONCLUSIONS: Stress is Present in every job. Though stress is unavoidable, stress may cause several undesirable consequences, and hence it is necessary to make every possible effort to reduce stress. It is not only the responsibility of people who undergo stress but even managements have to deal with the stress among employees and adopt stress relieving strategies.

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